

Impact of Intellectual Property Rights Protection on domestic music consumption: an empirical analysis

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Abstract

Digitization is radically changing everyday life, particularly the way music is experienced. Today, platforms like Spotify allow users to access and stream music anytime, anywhere. This shift has not only transformed the way music is created, accessed, and shared, but has also influenced the development of national policies regulating its distribution. In this paper, we examine how Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) protection affects the consumption of domestic music. Using Spotify data, we built a cross-sectional dataset covering 68 countries with “Top Songs of 2024” or “Top 50” playlists. We compared the nationality of the artists with the countries where their songs achieved success. Our analysis shows that the share of domestic music varies widely across countries and does not follow global patterns of IPR protection. Regression results reveal that the level of IPR protection has no significant impact on the presence of local artists. Instead, factors like market size and linguistic context, particularly being an English-speaking country, emerge as the main drivers of domestic music consumption. These findings suggest that demographic and cultural characteristics, rather than legal protection alone, play a central role in shaping the visibility of national music industries in an increasingly globalized streaming environment.

1 Introduction

The digitalization era has profoundly reshaped the global music market, reducing marginal costs associated with content production and distribution (Bello and Garcia, 2021). In 2016, digital sales already accounted for more than half of the revenues of the music industry (Coelho and Mendes, 2019). This change has raised important questions about cultural outcomes (Bello and Garcia, 2021). Contrary to early predictions that access to global catalogs would homogenize tastes through Cultural Convergence (Ferreira and Waldfogel, 2010; Waldfogel, 2018), empirical evidence reveals a counter-trend: a rise in Cultural Divergence characterized by a heightened preference for local artists, known as “home bias” (Achterberg et al., 2011; Way et al., 2020), leading to greater diversity in domestic music charts across songs, artists, and labels. The rise of local content is linked to the “random long tail” (Aguair and Waldfogel, 2018), where lowered barriers allow niche or previously rejected

cultural products to find an audience, making the market more diverse and unpredictable. However, this digital shift presents a dual challenge for the industry. While the rise of piracy, epitomized by Napster in 1999, significantly weakened effective copyright protection and collapsed traditional revenue (Waldfogel, 2020), the concurrent reduction in production, promotion, and distribution costs mitigated the threat to creative supply. Empirical evidence shows that the volume and quality of new music did not decline in the post-Napster era (Waldfogel, 2020), partly because lower costs preserved incentives for domestic creation and partly thanks to the growth of legal streaming alternatives such as Spotify (Verma, 2015). Concurrently with this evolving landscape, economic literature attributes a vital role to Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) in encouraging innovation, technological progress, and economic growth. However, the empirical link between IPR strength and economic performance remains complex and heavily dependent on institutional quality. On the one hand, researchers such as Torun and Cicekci (2007), cited in Neves et al. (2021), argue that IPR protection has a positive impact on innovation. On the other hand, Grossman and Helpman (1991) and Boldrin and Levine (2009), among others, find that protection should be reduced to foster creation and growth (Neves et al., 2021). To account for this ambiguity and the underlying institutional heterogeneity, our analysis controls for structural variables such as political instability, corruption levels, and linguistic factors (e.g., English proficiency). Crucially, the impact of IPR varies with countries’ levels of economic development. While strong protection is essential in advanced economies, its effect is weaker or insignificant in developing countries (Ginarte and Park, 1997). In these contexts, weak protection is seen as the most effective way to encourage imitation and knowledge diffusion, supporting the view that nations gain incentives to strengthen IPR once their domestic research sector reaches a ”critical size” (Ginarte and Park, 1997). This paper integrates these findings to address a crucial gap: given the rising success of domestic music driven by digital market access, how does the structure and strength of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), measured across varying institutional dimensions and development levels, specifically influence domestic production and the international trade flows in the contemporary digital ecosystem?

2 Data and Methodology

2.1 Data Collection and Dataset Construction

To examine the relationship between intellectual property rights (IPR) protection, proxied by an established official index, and domestic music consumption, we constructed a novel cross-sectional dataset covering 68 countries for the reference year 2024. The dataset integrates music consumption metrics obtained from digital streaming platforms with macroeconomic and institutional indicators sourced from official international databases. All data used in this study are freely accessible and contain no proprietary elements. All code and supplementary materials for dataset construction and replication of the analysis are available upon request. The data processing and statistical analyses were conducted using Python and R.

Primary data on music consumption were retrieved from Spotify, the world’s largest audio streaming subscription service. Using the Spotify Web API via Python, we collected for each

country in the sample the “Top Songs of 2024” playlists. In cases where the annual chart was not available through the API, we used the “Top 50” or “Viral 50” weekly charts (referenced to October 2024) as proxies for current local music preferences. To avoid seasonal distortions caused by Christmas releases, tracks from November and December were excluded from the compilation.

The raw dataset consisted of chart entries containing track-level metadata, including track name, artist name, and Spotify track ID. A key and critical step in the data construction involved determining the nationality of each artist. We adopted a semi-automated approach: artists were first matched to their country of origin using available metadata, followed by manual verification to ensure accuracy, particularly for countries with a high prevalence of domestic artists. A binary dummy indicator was then assigned to each track, taking the value 1 when the artist’s country of origin matched the country of the chart (e.g., an Italian artist appearing in the Italian Top 50), and 0 otherwise. These values were subsequently aggregated at the country level to compute the Local Music Share variable, defined as the proportion of chart entries attributable to domestic artists.

Data on intellectual property protection were obtained from the 2024 International Property Rights Index (IPRI). We specifically relied on the Intellectual Property Rights sub-index rather than the aggregate index score, as this allows us to focus on copyright-related institutional protections while excluding broader physical property rights components. In addition, we incorporated several institutional variables (rule of law, control of corruption, and political stability), measured on a 0–10 scale. These indicators capture broader governance conditions that may influence both the enforcement and effectiveness of IPR frameworks, as documented in the 2024 IPRI report. The reference year for all these variables is 2024, as comparable and complete information for 2025 was not yet available across countries at the time of data collection.

Additional control variables were included to account for cross-country differences in economic development and market size. GDP per capita (log-transformed) and population size (log-transformed) were retrieved from the World Bank Open Data for the year 2024. Data on digital infrastructure, proxied by the Internet Penetration Index¹, were also collected from the World Bank database; however, the reference year is 2023 due to substantial missing values in the 2024 release.

The final dataset was constructed by merging all the sources using ISO 3166-1 alpha-3 and alpha-2 country codes as matching key. All merging procedures and dataset construction were performed in a Python environment.

2.2 Employed Variables

Our dependent variable, Local Music Share, is defined as the percentage of artist entries in a country’s top chart that are of domestic origin. This variable serves as a proxy for the relative dominance of local music production within the national market. It is computed by

¹The Internet Penetration Index is computed as the number of people having access to the internet, in a specific country, with respect to the entire population of that country, in percentage terms.

summing the binary indicator identifying domestic artists and dividing by the total number of chart entries ($N = 50$) for that country:

$$\text{Local Music Share}_i = \left(\frac{\sum (\text{Artist Origin}_j = \text{Country}_i)}{\text{Total Artist Entries}_i} \right) \times 100 \quad (1)$$

The main independent variable, IPR Protection, corresponds to the Intellectual Property Rights sub-index from the International Property Rights Index (IPRI) 2024 report. This measure captures the strength of legal protections for intangible assets, including copyrights and patents, on a scale from 0 (weakest) to 10 (strongest). To isolate the contribution of copyright-related institutional quality, we did not rely on the aggregate IPRI score, which combines three components, Legal and Political Environment (LP), Physical Property Rights (PPR), and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). Instead, we used only the IPR dimension and included governance indicators related to the legal and political environment as separate control variables. This approach allows us to disentangle IPR-specific effects from those associated with broader institutional and property-rights frameworks.

To mitigate omitted variable bias, we therefore included several structural controls:

- *ln(GDP)*: the natural logarithm of the Gross Domestic Product per capita (current US), at country-level. It controls for the purchasing power of consumers, as wealthier nations may have more developed creative industries. The reference year is 2024.
- *ln(Pop)*: the natural logarithm of the total population. It controls for the "Home Market Effect", positing that larger countries can better sustain a domestic music industry due to internal demand. The reference year is 2024.
- *Net Penetration*: the well-known international Internet Penetration Index, originally measured as the share of individuals per country that have access to the internet (percentage) with respect to the total population of that country. For comparability reasons and coherence with the other variables, we applied a transformation in order to express it in range [0 (no internet coverage)- 10 (complete coverage)]. It is a valid measure to quantify the accessibility to the internet and related services, such as joining music platforms as Spotify.
- *English Speaking*: a binary variable taking the value of 1 if English is a primary or official language for the specific country, and 0 otherwise. It controls for the linguistic advantage of Anglosphere nations (i.e., Australia, Canada, Ireland, New Zealand, Singapore, South Africa, United States, United Kingdom), whose domestic music output overlaps with the dominant global market.
- *Rule of Law* : it measures agents' confidence and behavior according to the rules set of their society. Specifically, it measures the quality of contract enforcement, property rights, police, and courts, as well as the likelihood of crime and violence (Levy-Carciente, 2024). Its scale is [0 to 10].

- *Control of Corruption* : an index that measures the extent to which public power is exercised for private gain. According to the IPRI 2024 Report, corruption influences people’s confidence in the existence of protection and enforcement of property rights, and it also affects the degree of ”informality” in the economy, which is a deterring factor to the expansion of respect for legal private property. It ranges from 0 to 10.
- *Political Instability* : it endorses incentives to obtain or extend ownership and management of properties. The higher the likelihood of government instability, the less likely people will be to obtain property and develop trust according to the rights attached (Levy-Carciente, 2024). Its scale is [0 to 10].

The institutional controls (Rule of Law, Control of Corruption, Political Instability) were included in alternative specifications to test for broader institutional effects.

2.3 Empirical Analysis

We employed an Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) multivariate regression model to estimate the effect of IPR protection on local music consumption, measured through the Local Music Share variable. Although four specifications were estimated, the baseline econometric model (Model 3) is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Local Music Share}_i = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{IPR}_i + \beta_2 \ln(\text{GDP}_i) + \beta_3 \ln(\text{Pop}_i) \\ & + \beta_4 \text{English Speaking}_i + \beta_5 \text{Net Penetration}_i + \epsilon_i \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where i denotes the country, β_1 is the coefficient of interest, which measures the marginal effect of IPR protection on local music share. The other beta coefficients measure the impact of the related variable on the target variable, while ϵ_i is the residual term.

The following section first presents the descriptive analysis used to explore key bivariate relationships. We then estimated four model specifications: (Model 1) a naive bivariate model; (Model 2) a model controlling for economic size; and (Model 3) the full specification including cultural and infrastructural controls. Finally, we conducted robustness checks using broader institutional indicators to address potential multicollinearity between copyright-specific measures and overall governance quality (Model 4). All model equations are reported in this section.

Model 1:

$$\text{Local Music Share}_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{IPR}_i + \epsilon_i \quad (3)$$

Model 2:

$$\text{Local Music Share}_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{IPR}_i + \beta_2 \ln(\text{GDP}_i) + \beta_3 \ln(\text{Pop}_i) + \epsilon_i \quad (4)$$

Model 4 (robustness control):

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Local Music Share}_i = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{IPR}_i + \beta_2 \ln(\text{GDP}_i) + \beta_3 \ln(\text{Pop}_i) \\ & + \beta_4 \text{English Speaking}_i + \beta_5 \text{Net Penetration}_i \\ & + \beta_6 \text{Rule of Law}_i + \beta_7 \text{Political Instability}_i \\ & + \beta_8 \text{Control of Corruption}_i + \epsilon_i \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

3 Results

3.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 presents the summary statistics for the variables employed in the analysis. The institutional indicators display substantial cross-country variation: scores for IPR Protection, Rule of Law, and Control of Corruption range widely, reflecting heterogeneous governance environments across the 68 countries in the sample. Economic development also varies considerably, as shown by the dispersion in log GDP per capita and log population size, suggesting notable differences in income levels and market size. Finally, the Net Penetration index exhibits a relatively high mean but a wide range, indicating uneven digital infrastructure across countries.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Median	SD	Min	Max	Range
IPR Protection	3400	5.92	5.85	1.22	3.00	8.60	5.60
Ln(GDP)	3250	9.86	10.06	1.17	6.69	11.83	5.14
Ln(Pop)	3350	16.89	16.76	1.49	12.91	21.10	8.18
Control of Corruption	3400	5.91	5.95	2.13	1.70	9.80	8.10
Political Stability	3400	5.28	5.65	1.57	1.00	7.90	6.90
Rule of Law	3400	5.87	5.85	1.95	0.60	8.90	8.30
Net Penetration	3250	8.57	8.85	1.36	2.74	10.00	7.26

Notes: Missing values for the variables Ln(GDP), Ln(Pop) and Net Penetration treated as NA and removed.

To further examine the geographical distribution of music consumption and IPR protection, we mapped their global patterns. Figures 1 and 2 compare the IPR Index and Local Music Share across all countries in the sample. Figure 1 illustrates a clear "North-South" institutional divide, with Western Europe, North America, and Oceania exhibiting the strongest protection. However, Figure 2 reveals a different pattern: high levels of domestic music consumption are found not only in the Global North (such as in the U.S. and Italy) but also in major emerging economies, including Brazil and India. In contrast, countries like Canada and Australia, despite strong IPR protection, show very low domestic shares and rely almost entirely on imported music. Taken together, these maps suggest that strong copyright protection does not automatically translate into greater domestic music consumption. Other factors, such as cultural dynamics, language, and market size, likely play an important role together with formal legal frameworks.

This type of heterogeneity in domestic music consumption is further analyzed in Figure 3, which compares the 15 countries with the highest and lowest deviations from the global average share of domestic artists (42.3%). Countries on the right-hand side, such as Nigeria, Turkey, Egypt, India, and Brazil, show large positive deviations, meaning that local artists appear in their charts far more often than the global benchmark would suggest.

In contrast, countries on the left-hand side, including Australia, Austria, Switzerland, New Zealand, and several Latin American economies, display strong negative deviations, indicat-

Figure 1: Spatial distribution of IPR Protection across countries (2024)

Figure 2: Spatial distribution of domestic music consumption across countries (2024)

Figure 3: Market Polarization: best producers vs. top importers of music at country-level (2024)

ing a higher presence of foreign artists in their Top 50 charts. These markets are more closely aligned with global music trends, with domestic artists playing a smaller or irrelevant role. Overall, the figure shows a clear polarization: some countries rely heavily on local music, while others depend more on international content. This pattern highlights how institutional, cultural, and market factors can shape the share of domestic artists in national charts. In other words, there is a clear evidence of the "Home (Market) Effect", where market size influences the capacity to sustain the domestic industry.

A key structural factor emerging from the dataset is language. Figure 4 compares the distribution of Local Music Share between English-speaking countries and the rest of the world. The difference between the two groups is substantial. English-speaking countries show markedly lower domestic shares, with a median close to zero and most observations below 25%. This pattern reflects the strong presence of globally dominant English-language music, which reduces the visibility of domestic artists in these markets.

By contrast, non-English-speaking countries display a wider distribution and significantly higher central values, with many cases exceeding 50%. In these markets, domestic artists face less direct competition from the global mainstream and are therefore more represented in national consumption patterns, benefiting from the linguistic barrier. This supports the inclusion of the English-language dummy as a relevant control in the regression analysis, as it captures a structural linguistic factor that could otherwise confound the relationship between IPR protection and local music outcomes.

We then examined the role of other control variables to better understand which country characteristics relate with domestic music share, especially given the limited explanatory power of IPR protection in the descriptive analysis.

Figures 5 and 6 present the relationship between Local Music Share and two indicators of economic development: log GDP per capita and the Net Penetration index. Both show only weak negative correlations. Although higher-income countries tend to exhibit slightly

Figure 4: Does English language affect local music consumption? Distribution of Local Music Share between English-speaking countries and the rest of the world.

lower domestic shares, the variation across income levels is substantial and does not indicate a clear pattern. A similar result emerges for digital infrastructure: countries with high internet penetration display very different levels of local music share, with no strong visible trend.

Taken together, these results indicate that neither income nor digital infrastructure alone explains cross-country differences in domestic music consumption. This highlights the need for a multivariate analysis that jointly considers economic, cultural, and institutional factors.

However, the relationship between IPR and Local Share appears to be more complex. Figure 7 plots the relationship between IPR protection and the share of domestic artists in national charts, using global averages (IPR = 5.9; Local Share = 42.3%) as reference points to classify countries into four groups. Although no strong linear relationship emerges, the distribution highlights several meaningful patterns.

Countries in the upper-right quadrant combine strong IPR protection and high local music share. This group includes several large emerging markets (e.g., Brazil, Turkey, Mexico) as well as high-income economies such as Italy and France. These cases suggest that strong institutional frameworks can coexist with, or possibly support, active domestic music markets.

The upper-left quadrant contains countries with weak IPR protection but high local production, such as Nigeria, Egypt, India, and Vietnam. Here, cultural factors, language, and strong local industries appear to play a larger role than formal legal protection.

In the lower-left quadrant, some countries show both weak IPR protection and low local share, including several smaller Latin American and African markets. These outcomes may reflect structural constraints such as limited industry capacity, smaller audiences, or stronger exposure to global content.

Finally, the lower-right quadrant gathers countries with strong IPR protection but low do-

Figure 5: Does wealth (log GDP) affect local music consumption?

Figure 6: Does digital infrastructure (Net Penetration) affect local music consumption?

Figure 7: IPR Protection vs. Local Music Share: a classification by legal protection and domestic production

mestic production, including Singapore, Australia, Austria, Luxembourg, and Ireland. Many of these are English-speaking or highly globalized markets where domestic artists compete directly with international English-language content.

Overall, the figure shows that IPR protection alone does not explain differences in local music share, but it helps distinguish different country profiles. Cultural, linguistic, and market factors interact with legal institutions, shaping whether strong IPR environments translate into greater domestic music production. Moreover, while IPR may be important for monetization, it is not sufficient to drive popularity, which reinforces the need for a multivariate regression approach that accounts for additional sources of variation.

3.2 Regression results

Before estimating the models, all countries with missing values in any of the variables were removed to ensure that the regressions were based on a consistent sample. This reduced the dataset from 68 to 64 countries and allowed all model specifications to be directly comparable. Table 2 reports the results from four OLS specifications estimating the relationship between IPR protection and the share of domestic artists in national charts. Models 1 and 2 serve as preliminary steps, while Model 3 represents the main specification. Model 4 introduces broader institutional controls to assess potential multicollinearity.

Model 1 shows no meaningful relation between IPR protection and local music share. The coefficient is small, negative, and not statistically significant (-1.41), and the model explains none of the variation in the dependent variable ($R^2 = 0.002$). Model 2 introduces basic economic controls (GDP per capita and population, in log scale). While population size emerges as a strong positive predictor, neither IPR protection nor GDP per capita is significant. The explanatory power slightly increases ($R^2 = 0.288$), but the model still does not establish any clear link between IPR and domestic music production. Taken together, these

first two models indicate that simple or purely economic explanations are not sufficient to account for cross-country differences in local music share.

Conversely, Model 3 incorporates cultural and infrastructural controls and provides the most informative results. IPR protection remains positive but statistically insignificant, suggesting that stronger IPR regimes do not directly translate into higher shares of domestic music consumption. However, two variables are consistently significant at 99% confidence interval: the population size shows a strong positive effect (14.58), indicating that larger markets tend to host more domestic artists in their charts related to smaller markets; the English-language dummy is large, negative, and highly significant (-37.52). English-speaking countries display substantially lower local shares, consistent with their greater exposure to and integration with the global English-language music market. Net Penetration index and log GDP per capita remain non-significant.

Model 3 achieves the highest adjusted explanatory power among the core specifications (Adjusted $R^2 = 0.347$), and the F-statistic confirms joint significance of the regressors.

Since IPR Protection did not show a significant effect in the previous models, we estimated an additional specification that includes three broader institutional variables that may influence a country's cultural and economic environment: control of corruption, rule of law, and political stability. However, these variables are strongly correlated with each other and with the main regressor (IPR Protection), which introduces substantial multicollinearity.

Model 4 adds these institutional indicators, and, as expected, it confirms the presence of collinearity. The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values for rule of law (11.33) and control of corruption (8.65) exceed conventional thresholds (of 5-6), and IPR protection itself also shows an elevated VIF (5.95). As shown in the correlation matrix in Table 3, these institutional measures are closely related, which makes it difficult to separate their individual effects.

As a result, the coefficient on IPR becomes statistically significant in this model, but this shift is driven by multicollinearity rather than by an underlying relationship. The institutional variables themselves are unstable and not statistically significant, further indicating distortions in the estimates.

For this reason, the improvement in adjusted R^2 (0.365) cannot be considered reliable. Model 4 is therefore not used for inference; instead, it serves as a robustness check that confirms why these highly correlated institutional variables should not be included in the main specification.

Across all models, IPR protection does not show a statistically significant effect on the share of domestic artists in national charts. Instead, two factors consistently explain cross-country variation in local music consumption. First, market size, proxied by log population, matters: larger countries tend to produce and consume more local music. Second, language plays an important role: English-speaking countries systematically display lower domestic shares, reflecting their strong integration into the dominant global music market.

These findings support the idea that institutional copyright protection alone does not drive domestic music production. Rather, demographic and cultural factors appear to be more influential in shaping the presence of local artists in national streaming charts.

Table 2: Determinants of Local Music Consumption

	Dependent variable: Local Music Share (%)			
	Simple (1)	Economic (2)	Full model (3)	Institutional model (4)
IPR Protection	-1.413 (3.712)	1.679 (6.582)	6.749 (6.365)	12.827* (7.167)
Ln(GDP)		-0.221 (7.423)	-3.795 (8.736)	-1.881 (9.276)
Ln(Population)		13.262*** (3.220)	14.578*** (3.061)	13.362*** (3.505)
English Speaking			-37.518*** (12.033)	-37.461*** (11.951)
Net Penetration			3.317 (4.545)	4.291 (4.561)
Rule of Law				-10.297 (6.281)
Control of Corruption				6.507 (4.873)
Political Stability				-4.504 (4.234)
Constant	50.085** (22.580)	-189.074** (86.442)	-229.766*** (83.431)	-226.784** (91.530)
Observations	64	64	64	64
R ²	0.002	0.288	0.399	0.446
Adjusted R ²	-0.014	0.253	0.347	0.365
Residual Std. Error (df)	35.412 (62)	30.403 (60)	28.428 (58)	28.023 (55)
F Statistic (df)	0.145 (1; 62)	8.104*** (3; 60)	7.686*** (5; 58)	5.530*** (8; 55)

Note: Reference year: 2024. Log(GDP) expressed in per capita terms. Standard errors in parentheses. * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix: institutional factors

	IPR Protection	Rule of Law	Corruption Control	Political Stability	Ln(GDP)
IPR Protection	1.000	0.870	0.807	0.653	0.850
Rule of Law	0.870	1.000	0.931	0.729	0.855
Control of Corruption	0.807	0.931	1.000	0.733	0.854
Political Stability	0.653	0.729	0.733	1.000	0.771
Ln(GDP)	0.850	0.855	0.854	0.771	1.000

4 Conclusions

This study examined whether stronger intellectual property rights (IPR) protection is associated with higher domestic music production, measured through the share of local artists appearing in national Top 50 streaming charts. Using a cross-sectional dataset of 68 countries for 2024, we combined streaming-based consumption indicators with economic, institutional, and cultural variables. The empirical analysis shows that IPR protection, as measured by the IPRI sub-index, does not have a statistically significant effect on domestic music share across countries.

However, demographic and cultural factors seemed to be relevant determinants: in fact market size, proxied by the logarithm of population, showed a strong positive effect, supporting the "Home Market Effect" idea, where larger markets sustain local industries, while we can observe that local artist visibility seems to be affected negatively by the involvement into the global English-language music, as indicated through the English-speaking dummy.

Additional exploratory tests confirm that neither economic development nor digital infrastructure plays a major role in shaping local music outcomes. The robustness check including broader institutional indicators highlights substantial multicollinearity, indicating that these variables are strongly related to IPR protection to be included jointly without distorting coefficient estimates. This reinforces the choice of the main specification (Model 3).

Despite the study providing a unique dataset, a precise IPR measure and a rigorous, semi-automated approach to determine artist nationality from Spotify chart data, this analysis has some limitations. The results are based on a single cross-sectional year, which prevents us from capturing potential trends or changes over time. A panel dataset covering multiple years would allow for a more detailed assessment of whether IPR reforms or shifts in market structure affect domestic music consumption in the longer run. In addition, other institutional or socio-economic factors, such as periods of national mobilization, could influence consumers' preferences and potentially increase support for domestic artists. Future research could also explore alternative measures of local music share, including different chart sources, weighting schemes, or streaming-based indicators that capture "depth" of listening rather than simple chart presence. These extensions would help provide a more comprehensive framework of the determinants of domestic music consumption.

5 Remarks

All the analysis has been developed in Python and R environments. Replication scripts, the dataset and additional materials are available upon request.

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